

PROPERTIES OF POROUS ARBOLITE BASED ON MODIFIED NON-FIRED ALKALINE BINDERS

F.D. Zhuraeva¹, S.R. Akhundzhanova², J.I. Kholikov²

PhD, Associate Professor, Tashkent University of Architecture and Civil Engineering¹

Senior Lecturer, Tashkent University of Architecture and Civil Engineering²

First-year basic doctoral student at the Tashkent University of Architecture and Civil
Engineering³

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20838453>

Abstract. *This study investigates porous arbolite produced with modified non-fired alkaline binders using electrothermophosphorus slag, Asmansay basalt, and agricultural wastes such as cotton stalks, rice husk, and kenaf shives. Experimental mixtures were tested under heat-moisture and natural curing conditions to evaluate workability, compressive strength, and the influence of basalt dosage on binder performance. Results show that basalt can partially replace slag while maintaining sufficient strength and improving technological properties. Under natural curing, basalt contents of 20–50% were effective, with 40% giving the best performance: 40–47 MPa after 7 days and up to 70 MPa after 28 days. The findings support sustainable, resource-efficient, cementless construction materials based on local industrial and agricultural wastes.*

Keywords: *porized arbolite, modified, unfired alkaline binders, electrothermophosphorus slag, basalt, kenaf husk, rice husk, cotton stems, strength.*

Introduction. An analysis of global experience demonstrates that broad opportunities for solving this complex of problems are provided through the use of alkaline binders and concretes based on them. These materials possess a number of physical-mechanical and technical-operational characteristics that significantly exceed the corresponding properties of many other mineral binders and composites produced on their basis. For their production in the Central Asian region, and particularly in Uzbekistan, raw material resources are available in the form of large-scale waste from the metallurgical, chemical, and energy industries, as well as agricultural plant waste.

The versatility of these materials is characterized by a wide compressive strength range: from 20 to 160 MPa for binders and from 0.5 to 150 MPa for concretes, with an average density of 200–3500 kg/m³. The prospects for the application of these binders are determined by the fact that their production is based on the utilization of industrial waste and by-products, including all types of granulated and dump slags, fly ash and ash-slag mixtures, as well as alkali-containing waste, among others [1]. This indicates that such binders can be produced in all regions of the world. At the same time, it should be noted that the utilization of industrial waste simultaneously addresses environmental and fuel-energy issues and also expands the raw material base for construction materials [2].

Significance of the Research. The development of resource- and energy-saving technologies for the production of thermal insulation material—porous arbolite based on alkaline binders with the addition of basalt as an aluminosilicate raw material—makes it possible to utilize agricultural waste and local basalt deposits, efficiently recycle industrial waste, produce new

construction materials, reduce environmental pollution, and contribute to lowering the cost of both the material itself and construction processes in general.

Experimental Program. The Central Asian republics possess sufficient reserves of raw materials for the production of alkaline binders and organomineral composite materials based on them. At present, these raw materials are partially utilized as additives in cement production [3].

The study employed local raw materials and industrial technogenic waste. The following materials were used as the aluminosilicate component (ASC) of the alkaline binder: Zhambyl electrothermophosphorus (ETP) slag and basalt from the Asmansay deposit. Cotton stalks, rice husk, and kenaf shives were used as organic aggregates in the investigations [4].

Methods of Physical and Mechanical Testing. For testing, cube specimens with dimensions of $20 \times 20 \times 20$ mm were prepared from paste of standard consistency. Heat and moisture treatment was carried out according to a 2+6+2 h regime at an isothermal holding temperature of 80–90°C.

In the production of foam concrete, the conventional technology was applied: the binder paste and foam were prepared separately and subsequently mixed together. The duration of the study of the hardening processes of binders and concretes was up to 360 days. The specimens were stored under the following conditions: under normal curing conditions—in a chamber with a hydraulic seal at 100% relative humidity; under water curing—in a water container in accordance with KMK standards. The storage temperature of the specimens was maintained at 20°C [5].

Specimens measuring $100 \times 100 \times 100$ mm were manufactured. The workability of the initial mixture was determined using a Suttard viscometer. The compressive strength of foam concrete and porous arbolite specimens was determined using a P10 hydraulic press. In order to determine the effect of basalt content on the strength of alkaline binder stone, several compositions were prepared and investigated for compressive strength under different curing conditions.

Fig. 1. Strength of binders after heat and moisture treatment depending on basalt content

As a result of the conducted research and processing of the obtained data for the investigated binder composition, the optimal formulations of modified alkaline binders were determined. Based on the analysis of the experimental data, strength graphs of the developed binders were constructed.

The analysis of the graphs showed that when basalt is used as an additive component, the strength depends on the amount of ETP slag and the type of alkaline component. With a binder composition ratio of 1:1 (ETP slag:basalt) in the presence of sodium disilicate with a density of 1300 kg/m³, the strength of the specimens decreases by almost 50% and amounts to 46 MPa after heat and moisture treatment, compared to 110 MPa for a similar specimen based on pure ETP slag. A similar trend was observed after 28 days following heat and moisture treatment, where the strength reached 63 MPa compared to 125 MPa for the pure ETP slag binder (Fig. 1).

When basalt is introduced in an amount of 20%, it is possible to obtain a modified alkaline binder based on sodium disilicate with a strength of 100 MPa after heat and moisture treatment and 110 MPa after 28 days, respectively. At a basalt content of 30%, the strength of the modified alkaline binder is 65 and 94 MPa; at 40%, 53 and 73 MPa; and at 50%, 46 and 63 MPa, respectively. At the same time, it becomes possible to reduce the consumption of ETP slag by up to 50% of the total raw mixture mass.

Fig. 2. Strength of binders under natural curing conditions depending on basalt content

Under natural curing conditions for 7 days, during the hardening of the binder in the presence of sodium disilicate, the optimal basalt content ranges from 20 to 50%, with the optimum value being 40% (from the standpoint of saving electrothermophosphorus slag while maintaining sufficient strength of the alkaline binder). In this case, the activity of the binders at 7 days of natural curing reaches 40–47 MPa with a sodium disilicate density of 1300 kg/m³. After 28 days of natural curing of the modified alkaline binder, the optimal composition also lies within the range of 20–50% basalt content, while the maximum strength is achieved at a basalt content of 40% of the total raw mixture mass, with the strength reaching up to 70 MPa (Fig. 2).

The results obtained after 7 days of natural curing indicate that the difference in binder strength with increasing basalt content is not as pronounced as after heat and moisture treatment. Even at a basalt content of 90%, the strength of the modified alkaline binder after 7 days decreases by only about 50% (30 MPa) compared with the binder containing 10% basalt (45 MPa). It was established that the strength values of the specimens after natural curing are relatively similar, whereas the strength of heat- and moisture-treated specimens decreases sharply with increasing basalt content.

From the above-described experimental investigations, it was established that the most effective use of basalt with a soda-based alkaline component is its application as an additive (up

to 30%) in order to reduce the consumption of electrothermophosphorus slag and to increase the workability of the modified alkaline binder.

Conclusion. The experimental findings demonstrated that basalt additive can be effectively utilized as an active mineral constituent in alkali-activated binders modified with sodium disilicate. The influence of basalt incorporation on the physical and mechanical performance of the binder system was comprehensively investigated, allowing the determination of its optimum dosage. The obtained results revealed that a basalt content ranging from 20% to 50% provides the most favorable conditions for the development of strength under natural curing. In particular, the incorporation of 40% basalt yielded the highest performance, resulting in compressive strengths of 40–47 MPa after 7 days and up to 70 MPa after 28 days of curing.

The analytical assessment indicated that, under natural curing conditions, the reduction in compressive strength caused by increasing basalt content occurred gradually rather than abruptly. This behavior can be attributed to the partial participation of basalt in alkaline reactions, which contributes to the densification of the binder matrix and promotes the formation of a more compact microstructure. In contrast, specimens subjected to heat and moisture treatment exhibited a pronounced decline in strength as the proportion of basalt increased. These observations suggest that excessive basalt content adversely affects the structural development of the alkali-activated system when thermal curing regimes are applied.

Furthermore, the results confirmed that the partial replacement of electrothermophosphorus slag with basalt not only decreases the consumption of slag resources but also enhances the technological and rheological characteristics of the modified binder. Consequently, the proposed approach offers significant scientific and practical advantages for the production of sustainable, resource-efficient, and environmentally friendly cementless binder materials. The identified relationships between basalt dosage, curing conditions, and strength development provide a valuable basis for the design and optimization of advanced alkali-activated construction materials with improved performance characteristics.

REFERENCES

1. Tulaganov, Kh. Kamilov, H. B. Fisher, P. Krivenko *Zur Extraktion wasserlöslicher Stoffe aus organischen Zuschlägen und Auswirkung auf erhärtende Bindersysteme*. Proceedings of the 16th International Baustofftagung, Bauhaus University Weimar, Weimar, 2006, Vol. 1, pp. 845–856.
2. Kh. Kh. Kamilov *Technology and Properties of Arbolite Based on Non-Fired Binder and Agricultural Waste*. Abstract of PhD Dissertation in Engineering Sciences. Tashkent, 1997, 20 p.
3. O. Kasimov (2023). *Formation of the Structure of Arbolite and Its Influence on the Strength Characteristics of the Material*. Central Asian Journal of Education and Innovation, 2(11 Part 2), 115–118.
4. I.K. Kasimov, Kh. Kh. Kamilov, A. A. Tulaganov (1989). *Composition, Properties, and Technology of Slag-Alkaline Arbolite Based on Agricultural Waste*. *Slag-Alkaline Cements, Concretes and Structures*, Abstracts of Reports, pp. 152–153.
5. O.B. Kosimov, T.S. Aubakirova, N.H. Mirzakobilov (2023). *Studies of the Kinetics of Structure Formation of Slag-Alkaline Arbolite*. Central Asian Journal of Education and Innovation, 2(11 Part 3), 89–94.